

PROTECTIVE REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH, MOTHERHOOD AND CHILDHOOD

Axunova Nilufar

Center for Professional Development of Medical Staff,
"Nurses with higher education"
chair assistant

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Annotation: The study focuses on the level and trends of adolescent pregnancy rate (per thousand currently married adolescent women) in India in the last two decades, based on cross-sectional data from three different periods, DLHS-1 (1998–99), DLHS-2 (2002–04) and DLHS-3 (2007–08). Further, the determinants of adolescent pregnancy and its effects are analyzed using the DLHS-3 data, which used a multi-stage stratified systematic sampling design. The sample size of this study was 18,709 pregnancies that occurred to 14,006 currently married adolescent (15–19 years) women. Chi-square tests and logistic regression were used to examine the association between pregnancy outcomes (live birth vs. abortion/stillbirth) and health complications with socioeconomic variables and maternal-child health (MCH) service utilization.

Keywords: health services, vaginal delivery, illiteracy, sociocultural factors, demographic, World Health Organization.

During the periods of 1998–99, 2002–04 and 2007–08, the rate of adolescent pregnancy was 427, 467 and 438 respectively. In 2007–08, the proportion of live births (vs. stillbirth or abortion) was significantly higher among older adolescents aged 18–19 years (OR = 1.25, 95 % CI (1.08–1.44), $p < 0.001$) than among younger adolescent women of 15–17 years. The proportion of live births was also higher among women having 10 years or more education (OR = 1.26, 95 % CI (1.01–1.56), $p < 0.01$). The prevalence of live birth was significantly higher among women who had received some delivery advices (OR = 1.38, 95 % CI (0.96–1.95), $p < 0.01$), had consumed iron/folic acid tablets, (OR = 1.37, 95 % CI (0.89–2.11), $p < 0.05$), had received Tetanus Toxoid injection (OR = 2.29, 95 % CI (1.25–4.19), $p < 0.001$), while those with assisted vaginal delivery were significantly less likely to have a live birth (OR = 0.38, 95 % CI (0.21–0.68), $p < 0.001$). Adolescent women had 66.6 % delivery complications (i.e. any one problem) vs. 62.5 % among adult women (20–24 years), ($p < 0.001$).

Stillbirth and abortion are more prevalent among younger adolescents than among older adolescents, and among all adolescents than among adult

women. Delaying the first birth until age 20 appears to benefit both mothers and babies. Access to reproductive health services; timely and quality family planning services and safe abortion and delivery advice; tetanus toxoid and iron/folic acid for those married adolescents who do become pregnant could improve health outcomes.

About 16 million women 15–19 years give birth each year, which accounts for approximately 11 % of all births globally. The average adolescent birth rate in the middle- income countries is two times higher and in the low-income countries is five times higher as compared to high-income countries. Adolescent pregnancy can lead to morbidities (such as sexually transmitted diseases), mental disorders (such as depression) as well as higher neonatal mortality. These are the high-risk births for both mother and child. They are also high-cost births when the associated negative effects on quality of life and the role of women in society are considered.

The term ‘adolescence’ is variously defined. It is “the period of transition from childhood to adulthood, encompassing both the development to sexual maturity and to psychological and relative economic independence”. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the transition from childhood to adulthood may be referred to as adolescence or teenage, which is known as the period of 10–19 years.

Their age-related risk is compounded by malnutrition and inadequate antenatal care (ANC). Several medical complications, such as preterm birth, poor maternal weight gain, pregnancy-induced hypertension, anemia, and sexually transmitted diseases are associated with adolescent pregnancy.

The present study focuses on the level and trend of adolescent pregnancy in India. Further, the important determinants (such as sociocultural factors and health care services utilization) of adolescent pregnancy, the impact of early pregnancy on adolescent health in terms of complications during pregnancy, and problems during delivery are also investigated.

Three different time periods data, District Level Household and Facility Survey-I (DLHS-1, 1998–99), DLHS-2 (2002–04) and DLHS-3 (2007–08) were used to show the level and trend of adolescent pregnancy in India. Further, the DLHS-3 (2007–08) data is used to show the determinants and consequences of adolescent pregnancy in India. The DLHS-3 data used a multi-stage stratified systematic sampling design. The details of the sampling procedure are available in the DLHS reports.

In the present study, women aged between 15 and 19 years are considered as adolescents, and pregnancy occurred to them is termed as 'adolescent pregnancy'. A total of 18,709 pregnancies, that occurred to 14,006 currently married adolescent women (15–19 years) is used for analysis. The sample of adolescents of 15–17 and 18–19 years of age are 2701 and 11,305 respectively. Further, a sample of 73,455 currently married adult women of 20–24 years is taken to carry out a comparative analysis of pregnancy and delivery complications. In DLHS-I and DLHS-II, only information on the pregnancy of currently married women is available. Hence, pregnancy among unmarried adolescents is not addressed in the present study.

Variables

Several simple and compound variables have been constructed for analyzing the data.

Dependent variables

Dependent variables used in the study are also re-coded purposively. Pregnancy outcome is categorized as two parts, live birth and stillbirth/abortions, where abortion includes both spontaneous and induced. To see the effect of health care services utilization on adolescent pregnancy, the pregnancy outcome variable is again re-coded into live-birth and still-birth, but excluding abortion. The other dependent variables are: any pregnancy complications (which includes any common problems, i.e. swelling of hands, feet and face, paleness, giddiness/weakness, excessive vomiting, hypertension/high blood pressure or any major problems or any problems with the fetus; any major pregnancy complications (visual disturbance, excessive fatigue, convulsion, not from fever, jaundice, excessive bleeding and abnormal vaginal discharge); problems with fetus (weak or no movement of the fetus and abnormal position of the fetus); complications during delivery (including premature labour, excessive bleeding, prolonged labour, obstructed labour, breech presentation, convulsion/high blood pressure and others).

Statistical analysis

Bivariate and multivariate analyses are used to see an association between predictor variables and the outcome variables.

The analyses were conducted only for currently married adolescent women, considering their last pregnancy. The pregnancy rate among adolescents is shown in a number of pregnancies per thousand adolescent women. The author performed further analyses in two stages. In the first stage, differentials in pregnancy outcomes among currently married adolescent women are observed

according to their demographic and socioeconomic characteristics, such as age group of women, age at consummation, marital duration, place of residence, education level of women and their husbands, work status, caste, religion, wealth quintile of women. In the second stage, effects of women's age (i.e. 15–19 years and 20–24 years) on complications during pregnancy and delivery are assessed.

The logistic regression model was used to analyze the effect of selected socio-economic factors on pregnancy outcome among adolescent women. Binary logistic regression was used to estimate the adjusted effect of background characteristics on pregnancy outcome. Chi-square tests were performed to determine the level of significance of the correlation between women's age and the pregnancy and delivery complications. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 20 (IBM Corp, Armonk, New York) was used for data analysis.

The present study found that the proportion of stillbirths and abortions were significantly higher among younger adolescents as compared to older adolescents (18–19). The pregnancy loss or undesirable and adverse pregnancy outcome (i.e. stillbirth and abortion) was significantly higher among all adolescent women from the highest wealth quintile than among those belonging to the lowest wealth quintiles, and the odds of having a stillbirth/abortion increased significantly with each step in wealth quintile.

The level of education of the respondents also showed a statistical difference with the prevalence of stillbirths and abortion, where stillbirth and abortion are found to be significantly higher among women having secondary education, but statistically lower for those with 5–9 years of education as compared to <5 years. Although still birth is directly associated with poor maternal health and more prevalent among women from socio-economically disadvantaged background, the prevalence shows little difference from the prevalence among rich and highly educated adolescent women. The reason could be, women with previous abortion experience have elevated risks for stillborn and prematurity. However, induced abortion may predispose to negative future pregnancy outcomes, including a higher rate of spontaneous abortion and ectopic pregnancy among wealthier and higher educated women. Further, sex-selective abortion of female foetuses is more common in the educated and wealthier households in India. Presumably, the reason is that they can afford an ultrasound and abortion services more readily than the uneducated and poor women. It is also evident that the probability of reporting

of a miscarriage increases with the level of education of women. Young women are particularly vulnerable to poor sexual and reproductive health in general, and they have especially poor access to safe abortion services, which leads to delays in obtaining services and reliance on unsafe providers. Besides, desire to defer first child or acceptance of family planning or spacing being more prevalent among women with higher income and education level.

In India, wide variation in the reproductive health status of adolescent women shows that state or district level strategies are obligatory to provide services to adolescent women for reproductive health needs. The use of contraception among married adolescents in India is despondently low among all groups. A study has found that the extent of adolescent fertility has been declined from 100 per 1000 in 1971 to 52 per thousand in 1999 in India. According to the World Bank, the adolescent fertility rate in India has been declining and is found 84, 82, 79 and 77 per 1000 women in 2008, 2009, 2010 and 2011 respectively. The present study has shown that the rate of adolescent pregnancy is much higher as compared to the rate of adolescent fertility in India, which is a clear indication of a considerable number of pregnancies that are unsuccessful (i.e. abortion and stillbirth). Since 1971, the proportion of adolescent fertility to total fertility rate has been decreased from 9.7 % to 8.1 Further, stillbirth and unsafe abortions have an adverse effect on women's health, particularly in their teenage. During the adolescent period, women are physically immature and psychologically unprepared to experience the long lasting blemish of an unsuccessful pregnancy on their physical and mental health. Again, the amalgamation of poor nutrition and early childbearing exposes young women to serious health risks during pregnancy and childbirth. Complications during pregnancy and childbirth are the leading causes of mortality of girls aged 15–19 years in developing countries. This study found slight differences, though statistically significant, in the prevalence of major pregnancy complications and problems during delivery between women of age group 20–24 and 15–19 years. It is also observed that women who became pregnant at the age below 20 years, experienced more prenatal complications compared to adult women. This finding is supported by the literature where it is reported that children born to adolescent mothers face a higher risk of dying than those born to women aged 20–24 years. Further, the high rate of prevalence of any one of common complications experienced by adolescents during pregnancy (62.4 %) and delivery (66.6 %) are subjected to their broad definition, and these complications can be fatal and may affect maternal and neonatal outcome. It is

also found that pregnancy complications and delivery complications are much more prevalent among teenage women than among older women . The present study also found low prevalence of live birth and high prevalence of stillbirth among adolescents who had undergone an assisted delivery. There is also possibility of induced labour or assistance required to deliver a still-born baby. Hence, preventing pregnancies to women younger than 20 may improve neonatal outcomes.

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